

THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF CREATIVE ABILITIES IN THE PERSONALITY OF A PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHER

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The 21st century is the century of creativity and thought. The educational process is the main driving force of this century. In particular, the primary education stage plays a decisive role in the formation of a human personality. In this process, the personality of the teacher is the main factor, and it is his creative approach that determines the effectiveness of education. Each child is unique in his own way, and the teacher should be a guide who discovers and demonstrates this uniqueness. Children of primary school age are at such a delicate and responsible stage of development that during this period it is necessary for them to form not only the skills of living in society, but also the abilities of independent and creative thinking. Unfortunately, some primary school teachers consider the most important task to teach a student only to read. Of course, the correct and effective formation of the reading skills of each child requires great patience, knowledge, pedagogical skills and responsibility from the teacher. However, being limited to this, that is, not being able to reveal the inner talent of students, is one of the urgent problems facing modern education.

In solving this problem, one of the most effective tools that allows developing the creative potential of students can be considered art reading lessons. Artistic activity has a great influence on the development of imagination, thinking and free thinking in children. Such subjects as fine arts, technology, music also make a significant contribution to this process. However, it is worth noting that the lessons of the native language, mathematics and natural sciences also have wide opportunities for developing students' creative thinking abilities. It is important that within these subjects it is necessary to create conditions for the child to freely search, create new ideas and freely express his thoughts.

In fact, creativity is the ability of a person to break away from existing patterns and discover his own unique, unique approaches. Depending on the didactic goals set in art reading lessons, the development of these abilities can be carried out through various methods and techniques. It is especially important to use innovative approaches to develop oral and written speech of students in primary school. In this regard, various types of activities such as creative games, role-playing scenes, composing poetry, writing stories can be

effective. Because children of this age are still interested in games and learn knowledge more easily through them. Therefore, teaching through games serves as an important tool in the primary education system.

One of the important tasks of pedagogy is to create a favorable environment and conditions that serve the comprehensive development of the creative activity of each child. At the same time, it is necessary to identify students who are strongly interested in certain areas, are distinguished by their aspirations and potential, and create the necessary conditions for them to fully demonstrate their potential. It is for this purpose that factors that serve to develop the creative activity of younger school-age students are of great importance.

Such factors include:

The introduction of innovative approaches aimed at forming students' readiness for creative activity.

Establishing effective cooperative relationships between the teacher and the student.

The use of innovative technologies in creative activity aimed at knowledge.

Today, heuristic and problem-based teaching methods are widely used in the educational process. They ensure that students acquire knowledge through independent research and are aimed at discovering new things.

Creative activity is closely related to the inner world, way of thinking and emotions of a person, and it is manifested through the following main qualities:

Creating with inspiration and enthusiasm - a person is inspired by creative situations, beautiful ideas and aesthetic experiences, enjoys them, and this situation strengthens his figurative and passionate thinking. A creative person is inspired by inner emotional strength and wholeheartedly accepts every innovation.

Openness to innovation and a unique perspective - a person with creative thinking tends to quickly absorb innovations, put forward unusual and unusual ideas. Such individuals are able to approach problems in a new way, deeply analyze conflicting situations, and draw creative energy from them.

Initiative and independent thinking - creative people are interested in finding new ideas and testing them in practice. They strive for innovation, think unconventionally, use different approaches, and maintain their originality.

Broad outlook and associative thinking - a creative person can connect ideas with other people's concepts, find their connections, and use them to create new knowledge.

Socio-moral harmony - creative people maintain freedom in their thoughts and actions, respecting the moral standards accepted in society. They are able to harmonize creative freedom based on the values formed in school, family, and other social environments.

Sensitivity in thinking and freedom of approach - they can see something new even in ordinary and familiar phenomena. They approach problems with a non-standard approach and overcome existing stereotypes.

Creativity in acquiring knowledge - a creative person is able to enter into a dialogue with the object being studied, independently choose methods of cognition and determine the relationship of the object with other objects, their functional place.

Analysis of the dynamics of processes and objects - he can track changes in objects, identify development trends and create new methods on this basis.

Theoretical thinking and the ability to put forward hypotheses - creative people create new hypotheses within the framework of their intuition and thinking, tend to develop scientific views, laws and theories.

Practical application of a creative approach - they demonstrate their abilities not only in theoretical, but also in practical activities. They test themselves and gain experience by participating in competitions, olympiads, projects.

In general, the primary school stage is not only an important stage in the process of acquiring knowledge, but also in the formation of a person, and during this period, stimulating creativity and teaching independent expression of one's own opinion should be one of the main goals of education.

Lessons in primary grades serve the function of not only imparting knowledge, but also educating, teaching thinking, developing speech, and forming a worldview. A creative teacher teaches students not only to remember, but also to think, ask questions, seek answers, and discover.

In addition, the modern education system is being formed in such a way that it aims not only to impart knowledge, but also to fully reveal the creative potential of each individual. From this point of view, the development of creativity is recognized as an integral part of the educational process. Creative education is the organization of the educational process in a new, unique way, based on unique methods and technologies, in which the leading role is played by such aspects as the student's independent thinking, an unusual approach to problems, and the ability to combine knowledge and skills.

Nowadays, creativity is increasingly used in educational practice. Research in the field of pedagogy is aimed at a deep analysis of the essence of this concept, as well as at identifying creative potential in the younger generation and finding ways to further develop it. Creativity is the ability of a person to act in complex and unconventional situations using their own thoughts in new, progressive ways.

Today, technological achievements around us - for example, the Internet, artificial intelligence, digital services and virtual environments - clearly demonstrate that all of them are the products of human creative thinking. The formation and strengthening of such thinking should be carried out, first of all, in the educational process, starting from childhood. Therefore, the introduction of creativity in education is one of the important factors that contribute not only to personal success, but also to the development of society.

In conclusion, creative abilities are the most powerful weapon of a primary school teacher. With this weapon, he introduces each child to reading, reaches their hearts and shapes them as real people. A creative teacher is a light directed towards the future of society. Therefore, creativity should be the focus of special attention in the process of training teachers.

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